

Data Pitch

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Online presence and Marketing Tools

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Abstract

This document outlines the work completed so far to deliver the online and offline marketing materials for Data Pitch, including website, social media and offline marketing.

Executive summary

This document lists the work carried out to create an online presence for the Data Pitch project and to promote it in high priority, relevant online channels. It also details the offline materials that have been developed for for marketing purposes.

For the online presence, the Data Pitch consortium has finished the following work:

- [Project website](https://datapitch.eu/)¹ - including information for key audiences detailing how they can get involved; and the development of news stories and blogs, highlighting key milestones and calls to action
- Social media channels: [Twitter](https://twitter.com/DataPitchEU)², [Facebook](https://www.facebook.com/Data-Pitch-402275080131867/)³ including creating an account on Buffer to schedule social media posts, and the development of graphic social media cards to use across channels with the new Data Pitch Branding.

For marketing, we have designed the following materials to promote the Data Pitch project:

- 2 Data Pitch logos: one long form to be used as the default logo across materials, and one short form logo for stickers and social media profiles.
- Two font series which will be used all through the documents about Data Pitch project, such as website, presentation slides, etc.
- Presentation template - both a blank template and a designed static presentation to be used to present the Data Pitch 'product' to new audiences
- Stickers
- Roll-up banner
- Postcard flyer
- Data Pitch Factsheet for the European Commission portal
- Brand guidelines for use of logos and other marketing materials

¹ <https://datapitch.eu/>

² <https://twitter.com/DataPitchEU>

³ <https://www.facebook.com/Data-Pitch-402275080131867/>

Introduction

This document will introduce the work we have done to establish Data Pitch's online presence and the marketing materials we have prepared to be used in various Data Pitch events.

For Data Pitch's online presence, we have created:

- [Project website](#) - including news stories and blogs, and designed Data Pitch web banner
- Social media channels: [Twitter](#), [Facebook](#)

The development of these channels is crucial for building the Data Pitch ecosystem and community over the coming three years.

For marketing, we have designed the following materials to be used at events and face to face meetings to give consistency and professionalism to the project:

- 2 Data Pitch logos, one long form, one short form, for use in appropriate channels.
- Two font series which will be used through the documents about the Data Pitch project, such as website, presentation slides, etc.
- Presentation templates - one branded blank template which can be used to create new presentations, and one corporate presentation which static graphics to be used to communicate the project to new audiences
- Stickers
- Roll-up exhibition banner
- Postcard flyer
- Brand guidelines

1. Data Pitch Website

[The Data Pitch website](#)⁴ is the major information hub and it aggregates all dissemination, engagement and communication activities of Data Pitch into one conclusive online presence.

On the website, interested parties can:

- Find out how Data Pitch can benefit them
- Get in touch with the Data Pitch team
- Find the latest news from Data Pitch
- Follow our social media accounts
- Subscribe to our mailing list in order to get the latest news about Data Pitch project
- Read and comment on the challenges during the submission period

In future users will also be able to:

- See which companies have been accepted onto Data Pitch and read case studies about them

⁴ <https://datapitch.eu/>

- Find impact metrics
- View the Data Pitch deliverables
- View the Data Pitch resources and online business tools
- View the webinars such as startup applications, online training etc.
- View list of mentors in the programme
- View list partners from the Data Pitch wider network
- Read articles and stories about the project's progress

2. Social media channels

We have developed the following social media channels for Data Pitch:

- Twitter: @DataPitchEU⁵
- Facebook: Data Pitch⁶

We have also created a Buffer account to schedule social media posts and created social media cards to make Tweets etc more visually appealing.

We will use these social media channels to:

1. Direct traffic to various pages of the Data Pitch website at relevant times, for example:
 - To submit a challenge idea
 - To apply to the call for a position in the programme
 - To read new blogs and news stories
 - To find out more about what Data Pitch can do for the different stakeholders.
2. To flag media coverage which either focuses on, or features Data Pitch (ie, coverage we have directly generated from our media work)
3. To point to other relevant 'curated' online content, for example:
 - Interesting news stories, articles and opinion pieces about open innovation, startups, data, European trading success
 - Other companies, programmes and accelerators innovating with data.
4. To engage in conversation with the extended Data Pitch network and answer their queries.

3. Marketing toolkit

We have designed a series of marketing materials to promote Data Pitch in various physical and online events. The following table gives more details about these assets and how they will be used:

Materials	Specification
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⁵ <https://twitter.com/DataPitchEU>

⁶ <https://www.facebook.com/Data-Pitch-402275080131867/>

Logos	Two designs of logo: 1. Long form logo ⁷ 2. Short form 'dp' logo ⁸
Fonts	Data Pitch will use two series of fonts on website and in presentations, they are: 1. Museo Sans (typeface font) and 2. Calibri (System font) ⁹
Presentation template ¹⁰	The presentation template provides 7 example pages including: • Front page • Title with body content • Two columns content • Other combinations of text and images • The presentation conclusion page
Sticker ¹¹	The size is 60mm x 60mm
Roll up banner ¹²	The size is 850mm x 2000mm
Postcard ¹³	A6
Social media banner ¹⁴	
Brand guidelines ¹⁵	

⁷ <https://datapitch.eu/resources/>

⁸ <https://datapitch.eu/resources/>

⁹ <https://datapitch.eu/resources/>

¹⁰ <https://datapitch.eu/resources/>

¹¹ <https://datapitch.eu/resources/>

¹² <https://datapitch.eu/resources/>

¹³ <https://datapitch.eu/resources/>

¹⁴ <https://datapitch.eu/resources/>

¹⁵ <https://datapitch.eu/resources/>